

MUDDY WATERS STILL MUDDY

A RESPONSE TO *A CRITICAL REVIEW OF COVID-19 ORIGINS:
"HIDDEN IN PLAIN SIGHT"*

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Roger Brent

On July 21, 2025, the second and final instalment of Dr. Robert Kadlec's "Muddy Waters Update" report on COVID-19 origins (officially titled *A Critical Review of COVID-19 Origins: "Hidden in Plain Sight"*) was published by the Scowcroft Institute of International Affairs, at the Bush School of Government and Public Service at Texas A&M University.¹

People who don't know Dr. Kadlec should. In early 2020, Kadlec, then Assistant Secretary for Preparedness and Response at the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, and Dr. Peter Marks, then head of the division at the U.S. Food and Drug Administration responsible for regulating vaccines and other biologics, conceptualized and then executed Operation Warp Speed (OWS), the successful COVID-19 vaccine effort.

The OWS vaccines saved millions of American lives, tens of millions worldwide. Given contemporary political opposition to mRNA vaccines, it's important to note the first two (from Pfizer/BioNTech and Moderna) were mRNA vaccines, and that this technology had been scaled in part thanks to significant U.S. Department of Defense investments during the 2010s precisely to enable quick production and deployment against new infectious diseases. Both BioNTech and Moderna had been pursuing personalized anticancer mRNA vaccines; Moderna already had had an infectious-disease vaccine program. But when SARS-CoV-2 appeared, both companies shifted staff and budgets to move mRNA vaccine candidates into development within weeks.

For their work on Operation Warp Speed, I regard Kadlec and Marks as heroes and hope that in some less politicized future day a grateful nation will award them large, heavy gold medals to recognize the magnitude of that accomplishment.

Then, to this report. In this second Muddy Waters Update installment, Kadlec continues to operate as a kind of one-man DRASTIC group, making maximum use of openly available information, including information sources not usually considered.^{2,3} Among other sources, Kadlec draws on a) the virological and epidemiological literature, b) near-contemporaneous scientific papers from military and civilian scientists in Wuhan and elsewhere, c) contemporaneous news reports and announcements from local and national civil sources and official Chinese

¹ Robert P. Kadlec, *A Critical Review of COVID-19 Origins: "Hidden in Plain Sight"* (College Station, TX: Scowcroft Institute of International Affairs, 2025), <https://bush.tamu.edu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/A-Critical-Review-of-COVID-19-Origins.pdf>.

² William Audureau, "Covid-19: How a Group of Amateur Investigators Pushed the Lab-Leak Theory," *Le Monde*, February 18, 2025, https://www.lemonde.fr/en/les-decodeurs/article/2025/02/18/covid-19-how-a-group-of-amateur-investigators-pushed-the-lab-leak-theory_6738298_8.html.

³ Katherine Eban, "The Lab-Leak Theory: Inside the Fight to Uncover COVID-19's Origins," *Vanity Fair*, June 3, 2021, <https://www.vanityfair.com/news/2021/06/the-lab-leak-theory-inside-the-fight-to-uncover-covid-19s-origins>.

Communist Party sources, d) 21st century Chinese military writings, e) additional primary U.S. and international sources such as the DEFUSE proposal.⁴

For this review, it's worth mentioning Kadlec's use of one particular primary source: patent applications. Patent applications require that an inventor show that the invention is useful; and the applications usually do so by showing the invention offers improvement over some inferior status quo. Thus, we learn that in 2020 inventors of a new disinfectant at the Wuhan Institute of Virology asserted that the disinfectants then in use corroded their autoclave seals.⁵ And that in 2019 other inventors asserted that in the biocontainment "animal cabinets" then used to transport infected laboratory animals outside of contained volumes, the filters could fail and do so without that failure being detected.⁶ A third patent application described an invention that seemed likely to fail. This application, from April 2019, described a new autoclave design in which the exhaust valve in the sterilization chamber is always open, with the exhaust filtered through a steam trap, HEPA filters, and activated charcoal.⁷ It seems likely that with such a design, any water or hot steam that might pass through the steam trap would turn the HEPA filter into a hot, soggy, mess. And in fact, we read that on 19 November 2019, the Wuhan Institute of Virology issued a fast track, sole source, procurement notice for an "air sterilizer" to sterilize the autoclave exhaust downstream of that filter setup.⁸

Kadlec's report is composed of hundreds of pieces of information of this sort. Most of those pieces of information are probative, but only very weakly, in the strict "Rule 401" sense in the Federal Rules of Evidence: having "any tendency to make a fact more or less probable than it would be without the evidence."⁹

Nonetheless, there are a great many pieces.

⁴ Peter Daszak and Luke Hamel, "Project DEFUSE: Defusing the Threat of Bat-Borne Coronaviruses," grant proposal, EcoHealth Alliance, March 27, 2018, U.S. Right to Know, <https://usrtk.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/defuse-proposal.pdf>. Project DEFUSE was submitted to the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) under the PREventing EMerging Pathogenic Threats (PREEMPT) program.

⁵ Wu Jia et al., "Object Surface Disinfectant for High-Grade Biosafety Laboratory and Preparation Method Thereof," Chinese Patent CN 112262846 B, filed November 13, 2020, and issued November 9, 2021, <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN112262846B/en>.

⁶ Gao Ding et al., "Integrated Device for Biological Protection," Chinese Utility Model Patent CN 211375358 U, filed December 11, 2019, and issued August 28, 2020, <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN211375358U/en>.

⁷ Tang Huashen, "A Kind of Biosafety Autoclave and Sterilization Method," Chinese Patent Application CN 109966535 A, filed April 22, 2019, and published July 5, 2019, <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN109966535A/en>.

⁸ Wuhan Institute of Virology of the Chinese Academy of Sciences, "The Wuhan Institute of Virology of the Chinese Academy of Sciences Plans to Use a Single-Source Procurement Method to Publicize the Procurement of Air Incineration Devices and Test Service Projects," *China Government Procurement Network*, December 3, 2019, archived at <https://archive.is/jifqr#selection-373.67-373.129>. "It is proposed to adopt a single source to collect exhaust gas incinerators that are not directly used in autoclaves in China. The tail [exhaust] gas incinerator is a box structure, which is installed on the exhaust pipe outside the inner cavity of the sterilizer to realize the incineration [eg. sterilization] of all the media discharged from the inner cavity [of the autoclave]." Translation from Kadlec's report.

⁹ Fed. R. Evid. 401.

So, while the report falls short of being a case for the prosecution, it continues to fill out a picture of a city engaged in active research efforts on coronaviruses – surely by 2020 the largest concentration of such virological research and development (R&D) in the world. Research animals and samples resided in, and were likely transported among, different sites across the city: the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV) Zhengdian campus (home of multiple BSL-3 labs and the then newly operational BSL-4 facility, then the largest in the world); the “old” Wuhan Institute of Virology Xiaohongshan campus; the Wuhan University Institute of Animal Models; the Huazhong University of Science and Technology (Tongji Medical College); the Jinyintan, Union, and Zhongnan Hospitals; the Wuhan CDC; the Hubei CDC; and the Wuhan Institute of Biological Products (a branch of Sinopharm, which later in 2020 was growing SARS-CoV-2 in liquid cultures of Vero cells in 2000 Liter bioreactors).¹⁰ Kadlec’s report does not mention all of these sites but does mention another: Huazhong Agricultural University (HZAU). HZAU was then and is now a center for research on the two main coronaviruses that cause diarrhea in pigs, Porcine epidemic diarrhea virus (PEDV, an alphacoronavirus) and Porcine deltacoronavirus (PDCoV), and it operated at least one genomics facility that sequenced samples from other local institutions.

I’ll go ahead and define a concept, “biocontainment escape surface.” This term is analogous to a concept from cybersecurity, the “attack surface,” the sum total of points at which an entity is subject to cyberattack. The “escape surface” will be defined as the sum total of points by which a pathogen might escape containment, infect people, and so enter the human population.

A biocontainment escape surface will be comprised of but not limited to a) physical vulnerabilities, such as airlock seal failures, HVAC filter compromises, structural penetrations (electrical, plumbing), autoclave door seals, window/viewing port integrity, floor drains and liquid waste systems; b) weaknesses in standard operating procedures, such as entry/exit decontamination protocols, waste and animal handling and disposal procedures, sample transfer and transport protocols, equipment maintenance and operation protocols (so as to not produce aerosols), and emergency evacuation procedures; and c) human vulnerabilities, such as errors in PPE donning/doffing procedures, errors at hand-washing and decontamination stations, deficient staff experience or training, errors due to fatigue or complacency, or workplace cultures that fail to prioritize safety.

In January 2020, workers at the genomics facility at HZAU, the agricultural university, as was then international standard practice, uploaded to the NCBI (the world’s premier database of genetic sequences) Sequence Read Archive raw sequencing runs from a rice genome sequencing project. Later work by an international team of researchers analyzing uploaded raw sequencing runs reassembled a circular DNA construction (a “construct”) consisting of a BAC vector (a bacterial artificial chromosome) that also carried the genome of an entire, hitherto-

¹⁰ Ganesh Kumraj et al., “Capacity Building for Vaccine Manufacturing Across Developing Countries: The Way Forward,” *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics* 18, no. 1 (January 2022): 2020529, <https://doi.org/10.1080/21645515.2021.2020529>. In July 2020, after a 100 day crash construction project, WIBP opened a facility to grow SARS-CoV-2 virus in Vero cells to produce 100M doses of killed whole virus vaccine/ year (9). WIBP started the phase 1 and 2 clinical trials for its inactivated COVID-19 vaccine candidate on April 12, 2020. The construction team finished building the complex in July 2020, in just over 100 days and nights. My own rough calculation puts the volume of cell culture medium to grow enough SARS-CoV-2 in Vero cells to support production of 100M doses at $3-4 \times 10^4$ L/ year.

unknown, still-unacknowledged, MERS-like coronavirus.¹¹ Upstream of the cDNA for the viral genome, this construct carried a CMV promoter, a phage T7 promoter, and downstream, a Hepatitis delta virus ribozyme, and a bovine growth hormone poly A site. This sort of construct is used to carry out engineering and directed evolution work on positive stranded RNA viruses, and for recovery of live altered virus from transfected cells after rounds of engineering and evolution work are completed. The same sequencing upload that contained this infectious cDNA clone also included sequences of a second virus, a variant of the previously unknown MERS-like virus, but now engineered with its S (spike) gene cleanly replaced by the S gene from MERS itself. So, two previously unknown coronaviruses, one in an engineering construct. The WIV outsourced sequencing to other sequencing centers, and HZAU operates public technical platforms including sequencing services that are open to universities, enterprises, and testing organizations.^{12,13} Presumably, the viral genomes were accidentally sequenced, as contaminants, and uploaded in HZAU's rice genomic datasets.¹⁴

An earlier analysis by the same group of international researchers of sequences uploaded from Huazhong Agricultural University in 2017 and 2018 reassembled an entire sequence for yet another previously unknown MERS-related virus, the sequence of Japanese Encephalitis Virus (an unrelated positive strand RNA virus, a flavivirus, and a BSL-3 level pathogen), and stretches of mitochondrial DNA from pigs, humans, and camels (*Camelus dromedarius*, the original host for MERS). These viral, pig, human, and camel sequences, from 2017 and 2018 were also uploaded as contaminants, this time in cotton genomic datasets.¹⁵

The reverse genetics system carried on the BAC construct has not been published. None of the three still-novel MERS-related viruses nor any engineering or directed evolution work on them has been described in subsequent academic publications.

So, in Wuhan, the biocontainment escape surface was enormous. And in fact, from the contaminating viral DNA sequences, at least in 2017, 2018 and 2020, one can assert that the escape surface leaked.

¹¹ Adrian Jones et al., "Discovery of a Novel Merbecovirus DNA Clone Contaminating Agricultural Rice Sequencing Datasets from Wuhan, China," *Journal of Bioinformatics and Systems Biology* 7 (2024): 139–156, February 20, 2023, <https://www.doi.org/10.26502/jbsb.5107086>.

¹² Jon Cohen, "Wuhan Coronavirus Hunter Shi Zhengli Speaks Out," *Science* 369, no. 6503 (2020): 487–488, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.369.6503.487>. This information is in Zhi's accompanying written responses, "Reply to Science magazine." "(2) Does your group extract viruses from biological samples and do the sequencing or does that take place elsewhere? A: We isolated viruses or extracted virus RNA from biological samples in the lab. The sequencing was done mostly in Wuhan."

¹³ Huazhong Agricultural University Financial & Asset Management Department, "我校大型仪器公共技术平台参加2024年度湖北省科技资源开放共享服务展示会" [Our University's Large-Instrument Public Technical Platform Participates in the 2024 Hubei Province Science & Technology Resources Open-Sharing Service Exhibition], March 29, 2024, <https://cwb.hzau.edu.cn/info/1079/4759.htm>.

¹⁴ Jones et al., "Novel Merbecovirus."

¹⁵ Daoyu Zhang et al., "Unexpected Novel Merbecovirus Discoveries in Agricultural Sequencing Datasets from Wuhan, China," arXiv, June 6, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2104.01533>.

Yet, the report still falls short of being a case for the prosecution. Despite the hundreds of particles of technically probative evidence, to my mind this report might not convince a grand jury to issue an indictment. Given the American proverb that a competent district attorney can convince a grand jury to indict a ham sandwich, gaining an indictment would seem a low bar.¹⁶

The reason the report might fall short is that a prosecutor who seeks an indictment traditionally presents evidence in the context of a “theory of the case,” a narrative that ties all the evidence together.

In Kadlec’s report, we have a picture of coronavirus research and development as a local industry, with widespread local use of transgenic mice with human ACE2 and DPP4 receptors for vaccine trials, ferrying of infected animals across town, corroding of autoclave seals, short-suspense orders for autoclave exhaust sterilizers, engineering-ready infectious respiratory virus clones spilled into the rice genome samples... all of this going on in an atmosphere of civil-military fusion in which military and civilian researchers have commercial ties to biopharma and vaccine companies. This picture would make the story in Kadlec’s report, a possible escape of a lab-developed SARS-CoV-2 into the human population, one of accidental infection. My imaginary prosecutor might argue that an accidental infection could be the consequence of activities that perhaps might be negligent, or even reckless. But it is also possible that an accidental escape might have been more similar to many aircraft and nuclear power accidents, that is, a consequence of chains of individually-unlikely events occurring over many person-years of operations. But any such picture lacks a story for why all this R&D activity might be happening. Nor for why SARS-CoV-2 in particular.

The report never ties itself to a single narrative, and at many places it seems to dance around the issues. A possible reason this report might lack such an explicit theory is that such a theory might be military, and monstrous. Moreover, such a theory might also take readers of the report farther into the realm of tinfoil-hat conspiracy than many would care to go. Even telling or repeating such ideas is a profoundly serious act, and scientists who wish to hew to their vocation (as I do) and who wish to retain the respect of their peers (as I do), must be immensely careful in what they articulate.

So, keeping this context in mind, Kadlec’s report suggests a reason particular coronavirus R&D activity might have been going on. It cites official military writing that speaks of the desirability of attaining “cognitive dominance” over the adversary.¹⁷ The report tells the story of work by Army General Dr. Yusen Zhou of the Institute of Microbiology and Epidemiology of the Academy of Military Medical Sciences (AMMS). Zhou’s previous coronavirus work was on SARS-CoV (SARS-1) and on MERS. In his work on MERS, Zhou’s group was known for development of a chimeric protein vaccines composed of the Fc chain of IgG (an antibody protein) and the MERS S protein’s receptor binding domain. These chimeric proteins made effective vaccines, and he and U.S. coworkers applied for and were granted

¹⁶ Sol Wachtler, interview by Marcia Kramer and Frank Lombardi, *New York Daily News*, January 31, 1985. District attorneys have so much influence on grand juries that “by and large they could convince them to indict a ham sandwich.”

¹⁷ Elsa B. Kania, “Minds at War: China’s Pursuit of Military Advantage Through Cognitive Science and Biotechnology,” *PRISM* 8, no. 3 (2019): 82–101, JSTOR, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26864278>.

U.S. and European patents on them.^{18,19,20} Zhou had also collaborated with Dr. Zhengli Shi at the Wuhan Institute of Virology on other aspects of MERS virology. On 17 November 2019, Zhou and members of his research group submitted a paper with Shi and her group that explored the ability of pseudotyped MERS-CoV to infect HEK293T cells exogenously expressing DPP4, or that expressed one of the Fc receptors (CD16A, CD32A, or CD64A). Their work showed that neutralizing monoclonal antibodies to the MERS-CoV-S (spike) protein bound the S protein, presumably inducing a conformational change that allowed the virus to enter cells via Fc receptors, a new route.²¹

The sequence of SARS-CoV-2 was released on 11 January 2020. On 24 February 2020, Zhou, together with coworkers from a second AMMS institute, the Institute of Military Cognition and Brain Science, filed for a patent on a recombinant protein vaccine against SARS-CoV-2. Kadlec knows a great deal of trying to test vaccine candidates quickly, and his report questions this timeline; if Zhou and coworkers had started work on 11 January, 44 days from sequence to mice with antibodies in their serum against SARS-CoV-2 spike protein would be exceptionally fast work. However, as I cipher things out, such a timeline might be just barely possible. Zhou and coworkers had made analogous chimeric proteins before and were at least well positioned to carry out the requisite DNA construction parts of this work without any missteps; the recombinant protein described in the patent application was strictly patterned on the Fc-RBD vaccine constructs Zhou and his coworkers had previously developed against MERS.²² The description of the mouse immune response in the patent application does not rule out the possibility that the ELISA used to show serum immunity was set up to detect the faster-appearing IgM. And the first upload of SARS-CoV-2 sequence to NCBI, by another virology group in China, occurred two weeks earlier, on December 28, 2019. Still, the parsimonious explanation is that Zhou and coworkers had even more of a head start.

In work submitted April 2020, Zhou and coworkers tested SARS-CoV-2 infectivity in a transgenic mouse line (hACE2-KI/NIFDC) that expresses human ACE2 (the receptor that SARS-CoV-2 uses to infect human cells) in lieu of the mouse ACE2, under the control of the native mouse promoter. Such mice express human ACE2 in the same tissues and same amounts as mouse ACE2, with the consequence that some human ACE2 is expressed in some parts of the mouse brain. Assayed by RT-PCR, the brains of infected mice showed “high viral loads” and brain homogenates contained infectious virus.²³ Immunostaining of brain sections from the mice showed “robust viral spike protein

¹⁸ Yusen Zhou et al., “Advances in MERS-CoV Vaccines and Therapeutics Based on the Receptor-Binding Domain,” *Viruses* 11, no. 1 (2019): 60, <https://doi.org/10.3390/v11010060>.

¹⁹ Lanying Du et al., “Immunogenic Composition for MERS Coronavirus Infection,” U.S. Patent Application US20190328865A1, filed November 11, 2017, and granted August 31, 2021, <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20190328865A1/en>. and European Patent EP3541419B1, granted 5 January 2022.

²⁰ Lanying Du et al., “Immunogenic Composition for MERS Coronavirus Infection,” European Patent EP3541419B1, granted January 5, 2022, <https://patentimages.storage.googleapis.com/14/84/c3/96f36d7200e88d/EP3541419B1.pdf>.

²¹ Yushun Wan et al., “Molecular Mechanism for Antibody-Dependent Enhancement of Coronavirus Entry,” *Journal of Virology* 94, no. 5 (2020): e02015-19, <https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.02015-19>.

²² Yusen Zhou et al., “Novel Coronavirus COVID-19 Vaccine, Preparation Method and Application Thereof,” Chinese Patent Application CN111333704A, filed February 24, 2020, <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN111333704A/en>.

²³ Shi-Hui Sun et al., “A Mouse Model of SARS-CoV-2 Infection and Pathogenesis,” *Cell Host Microbe* 28, no. 1 (2020): 124–133, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chom.2020.05.020>.

expression ... in neurons, astrocytes and microglial cells.”²⁴ Subsequently, in November 2020, Zhou and other coworkers published studies in which the hACE2-KI/NIFDC humanized mice and wild-type primates were vaccinated with his group’s recombinant vaccine and then challenged with SARS-CoV-2. That second paper did not present data on viral load, neuropathology, or on the vaccine’s ability to protect the brain, even though the same scientists at the Institute of Military Cognition and Brain Sciences were listed as coauthors.^{25,26} The preprint of the paper preserved that institutional affiliation, while in the published version, the scientists’ affiliation is given instead as the Beijing Institute of Basic Medical Sciences.

In May 2020, Zhou and his coworkers submitted to the journal *Science* a paper that described the directed evolution of SARS-CoV-2 by serial passage through Balb/C mice to generate a SARS-CoV-2 variant that used the mouse ACE2 protein and infected normal mice. In the published paper in July 2020 Zhou was listed as deceased.²⁷ The inference is that sometime between May 2020 and July 2020, General Zhou died.

Although no published report from Zhou and his coworkers describes neuropathology of SARS-CoV-2 infection, other groups using other (K18-hACE2) humanized mouse lines do report encephalitis.^{28,29} In these mice, human ACE2 expression is under the control of the a different promoter, with the consequences that human ACE2 expression in the mouse brain is higher and that some olfactory sensory neurons (OSNs) in the nose ectopically express human ACE2 as well. In K18-hACE2 mice, those ACE2-expressing neurons provide a direct route for viral entry that bypasses the sites and sets of immune system cells whose normal operation generates the still-imperfectly-understood “nose-brain barrier” to viral infection.³⁰

It’s important to note that brain involvement in SARS infection is not considered normal. The transgenic mice mentioned above were infected by pipetting suspensions of virus into directly into their noses. In animal studies that use aerosols to infect, brain infection does not occur: even for K18-hACE2 mice, with human ACE2 expressed in some olfactory sensory neurons (OSNs), aerosol or droplet infection results in respiratory infection and anosmia without fatal brain invasion, and aged macaques and green monkeys challenged by aerosol show brain pathology

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Shihui Sun et al., “Recombinant Vaccine Containing an RBD-Fc Fusion Induced Protection Against SARS-CoV-2 in Nonhuman Primates and Mice,” *Cellular & Molecular Immunology* 18 (2021): 1070–1073, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41423-021-00658-z>.

²⁶ Shihui Sun et al., “Recombinant Vaccine Containing an RBD-Fc Fusion Induced Protection Against SARS-CoV-2 in Nonhuman Primates and Mice,” bioRxiv, November 30, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.11.29.402339>.

²⁷ Hongjing Gu et al., “Adaptation of SARS-CoV-2 in BALB/c Mice for Testing Vaccine Efficacy,” *Science* 369, no. 6511 (2020): 1603–1607, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abc4730>.

²⁸ Pratima Kumari et al., “Neuroinvasion and Encephalitis Following Intranasal Inoculation of SARS-CoV-2 in K18-hACE2 Mice,” *Viruses* 13, no. 1 (2021): 132, <https://doi.org/10.3390/v13010132>.

²⁹ Mariano Carossino et al., “Fatal Neurodissemination and SARS-CoV-2 Tropism in K18-hACE2 Mice Is Only Partially Dependent on hACE2 Expression,” *Viruses* 14, no. 3 (2022): 535, <https://doi.org/10.3390/v14030535>.

³⁰ Linda B. Buck, conversation with author.

consistent with hypoxia and microvascular injury with but only scarce viral signal.^{31,32} In humans, where SARS-CoV-2 certainly spreads by aerosols and droplets, the anosmia caused by SARS-CoV-2 is thought to be due to the destruction the virus causes to other cell types in the olfactory epithelium generically referred to as Olfactory Support Cells (OSCs); human olfactory sensory neurons (OSNs) do not express ACE2, and that path into the brain is blocked.³³ In autopsies of people who died of SARS-CoV-2 classical viral encephalitis is rare. In one early multicenter study, 6/43 autopsied brains showed ischemic injuries, 37/43 showed generalized activation of microglia and 34/43 infiltration by meningeal cytotoxic T cells, but only 21/40 brains showed detectable SARS-CoV-2, as assayed by RT-qPCR and or immunohistochemistry against viral proteins.³⁴ A later study using the more sensitive ddPCR nucleic acid detection technology only detected viral RNA in 10/11 brains, did not find viral RNA in all brain regions and in all cases lower RNA levels than in respiratory tissues.³⁵

Later, in 2023, two of Zhou's coworkers, those formerly associated with the AMMS Institute of Military Cognition and Brain Science, now identified as at the AMMS Beijing Institute of Basic Medicine, published a review titled "Virus induced cognitive decline." True to its title, the review described mechanisms by which brain infection by different viruses, including SARS-CoV-2, might induce cognitive decline.³⁶ For whatever reason, this mini-review appeared in a biosafety journal. Moreover, the review's introductory paragraph mentions the importance of biosafety (reasonable, given the journal), but also that "black swan" events occur and that biosafety risks are associated with "not only cytometry instrumentation and samples, but also the people working with them." The reasoning for the authors' attention to black swan events and to flow cytometry in particular is not articulated. Certainly, flow cytometry and flow cytometric sorting is ubiquitous in modern virological engineering and evolution work, and it is used in deep mutational scanning campaigns, for example to isolate mutations in receptor binding domains of viral entry proteins that bind a virus's receptor more or less tightly.³⁷ In larger flow cytometers, leakage of aerosols is avoided by careful sample handling and attention to equipment operation and maintenance. But it was only in 2021, during the pandemic, that direct experimentation showed that the sample injection ports, automatic plate loaders, exit fans and waste tanks of benchtop flow cytometers also often leaked aerosols and droplets, even when properly

³¹ Valeria Fumagalli et al., "Administration of Aerosolized SARS-CoV-2 to K18-hACE2 Mice Uncouples Respiratory Infection from Fatal Neuroinvasion," *Science Immunology* 7, no. 67 (2021): eabl9929, <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciimmunol.abl9929>.

³² Ibolya Rutkai et al., "No Brain Invasion in Aerosol Infected Green Monkeys and Macaques," *Nature Communications* 13 (2022): 1745, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-29440-z>.

³³ Rafal Butowt et al., "Olfactory Dysfunction in COVID-19: New Insights into the Underlying Mechanisms," *Trends in Neuroscience* 46, no. 1 (2022): 75–90, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2022.11.003>.

³⁴ Jakob Matschke et al., "Neuropathology of Patients with COVID-19 in Germany: a Post-Mortem Case Series," *The Lancet Neurology* 19, no. 11 (2020): 919–929, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(20\)30308-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(20)30308-2).

³⁵ Sydney R. Stein et al., "SARS-CoV-2 Infection and Persistence in the Human Body and Brain at Autopsy," *Nature* 612 (2022): 758–763, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05542-y>.

³⁶ Chunxiao Du et al., "Biosafety and Mental Health: Virus Induced Cognitive Decline," *Biosafety and Health* 5, no. 3 (2023): 159–167, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bshealth.2023.04.002>.

³⁷ Tyler N. Starr et al., "Deep Mutational Scanning of SARS-CoV-2 Receptor Binding Domain Reveals Constraints on Folding and ACE2 Binding" *Cell* 5, no. 3 (2020): 1295–1310, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2020.08.012>.

maintained and operated.³⁸ The inference is that the authors of the article were concerned that flow cytometers can leak, that such leakage and black swan events can result in biosafety incidents, and that the authors are aware that infection by viruses, possibly connected with such incidents, can cause cognitive decline.

So: might General Zhou and coworkers have been trying to develop a contagious respiratory virus that could cause brain damage in unvaccinated people? To be used as weapon? Kadlec's report certainly hints at this possibility.³⁹ Again, it cites official military writing that speaks of the desirability of attaining "cognitive dominance" over an adversary.⁴⁰ It mentions the brain fog now sometimes reported by patients with long Covid. It reminds us of the precedent for use of brain-damaging viral weapons against enemies together with vaccines for one's own. The U.S. Cold War biological warfare program explicitly worked on this concept, using Venezuelan equine encephalitis (VEE), as a "humane" and "neuro-incapacitating" weapon, with a case fatality rate of "only" 1%, whose temporary effects on the enemy would include "extreme irritation, lethargy, discoordinated actions, temporary illness and lack of a will to fight."⁴¹

It's worth remembering that dependably, throughout 20th century history, some scientists have wished to build horrifying weapons, and those scientists' conception of and enthusiasm for the horrifying weapons did not always come from higher up. Certainly in the U.S. during the Cold War, there is a rich history of civilian and military scientists envisioning and then pushing to build truly appalling weapons, only to be overruled by saner political leadership.⁴²

³⁸ Avril Aspland et al., "Risk Awareness During Operation of Analytical Flow Cytometers and Implications Throughout the COVID-19 Pandemic," *Cytometry* 99, no. 1 (2020): 81–89, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cyto.a.24282>.

³⁹ Yuri Deigin, "Why Ralph Baric's Testimony Strengthens the Case for a COVID-19 Lab Origin," Medium, May 8, 2024, <https://yurideigin.medium.com/why-ralph-barics-testimony-strengthens-the-case-for-a-covid-19-lab-origin-81cf9c2acf71>. One of the members of the DRASTIC group, Yuri Deigin, citing Dr. Ralph Baric's January 24, 2024 Congressional testimony, has put forward an alternative explanation for why the Wuhan group might have been collecting so many coronaviruses and making chimeric viruses. In his testimony, Dr. Baric put forward the idea of a challenge panel, presumably a panel of chimeras with different S proteins, that spanned the endpoints ("bookends") of sarbecovirus diversity—SARS-1 at one end, highly divergent strains at the other—with a mid-range (~20–25% S protein sequence divergence) in between. The idea is that if a proposed broad spectrum vaccine or anti-S protein neutralizing antibody worked on both ends and on the middle, without promoting antibody dependent viral entry (already observed by Zhou and Li, see note 21), that vaccine or antibody would be likely to provide protection against the next coronavirus that emerged from nature.

⁴⁰ Kania, "Minds at War."

⁴¹ Henry J. Hearn, *Agent Summary Status Report on Venezuelan Equine Encephalitis* (Fort Detrick, MD: U.S. Army Biological Laboratories, 1966), U.S. National Archives.

⁴² Eldon W. Sams and Frank E. Rom, *Analysis of Low-Temperature Nuclear-Powered Ram-Jet Missile for High Altitudes* (Washington, DC: U.S. National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics, 1955), RM E55G21, <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/19930088872>. By 1958, and enabled by successful testing, this first idea had turned into Project Pluto, or the Supersonic Low Altitude Missile (SLAM). SLAM was to be a low altitude cruise missile, its ramjet powered by an unshielded fission reactor, to carry 16 hydrogen bombs, flying at Mach 3, devastating armies and cities immediately below it with an 150 Decibel shock wave and leaving behind it a trail of reactor fission products, ¹⁶N, ¹⁹O, ¹⁴C, and ⁴¹Ar newly generated from the air, and particles of unburned fissile material spalled off from the deteriorating insides of the open reactor. According to the Nevada National Security site, the aim was to "flatten, deafen and irradiate" people, armies, and cities below. And those effects were to be on top of the destructive effects of the hydrogen

If one leaves these shadowlands, what remains, from which the report continues to derive much of its force, is something passive and devoid of implied human intention: its portrayal of large-footprint virological research and development activities spread across multiple sites in a large 21st century city. Activities that could easily be seen as accidents waiting to happen.

And there also remain the report's hundreds of particles of other evidence. These cover many topics. Some of these are familiar, at least to biologists, in fact so familiar as to risk causing eyes to glaze over: the viral genome database gone offline, the dispersed geographical distribution of the species from which the viruses most closely related to different pieces of the SARS-CoV-2 genome were isolated, the absence of significant genomic variation among early isolates of the outbreak – operationally defining the new virus as well adapted to humans, and of course the very close resemblance of SARS-CoV-2 to the new SARS-related coronaviruses that were to be constructed for the unfunded 2018 DARPA DEFUSE proposal. Others will not be, including the September 2019 drill at Wuhan Tianhe airport simulating discovery of a single person infected with a new coronavirus in the WUH customs lane conducted in a “real combat style,” featuring real-time setup of a quarantine area, or the urgent, out-of-cycle biosafety training session at the WIV in November 2019, led by a Beijing security official who had conveyed a personal directive from Xi Jinping about a “complex and grave situation.”

The list of particles goes on. All certainly probative, in the Rule 401 sense, but weak. There is no grand jury empaneled. Nor is there a district attorney. A professional prosecutor here would be a good thing, because even zealous district attorneys operate under strict rules. In fact, in some U.S. states, including New York, California, and Colorado, if prosecutors know of exculpatory evidence, they are legally obligated to present it. In the future, a careful and principled prosecutor could go far. But for now, the ham sandwich remains unindicted.

In the future, there will be additional evidence. New open-source material, possibly including exculpatory evidence, will surface. If there are people who have stories to tell, those people may come forward. And of course, evidence and arguments and personal stories may emerge that support a zoonotic origin for SARS-CoV-2. In a less politicized future, it is possible to imagine some sort of two-sided inquiry, in which evidence for each possibility would be produced, questioned, weighed. However, in the current political environments, domestic and geopolitical, no such process has started, nor seems likely.

Like World War I for the 20th century, for the 21st century, the COVID-19 pandemic was a cataclysmic event. Millions died, and the survivors sought to make sense of and understand what had just happened. The effects of WWI on 20th century politics and human events reverberated for decades afterward. Today, in 2025, it seems possible that the political and cultural effects of the pandemic may also resonate for decades to come. The analogy to WWI is first to make the point that it took historians decades to arrive at any kind of consensus on the causes of that war.

bombs the SLAM would drop. After all 16 bombs were delivered, but before its work was done, SLAM was to destroy a final 17th target by crashing into it (kinetic kill), while at the same time igniting its last thermonuclear charge, which would further damage the final target (by vaporizing it), and at the same time evaporate the SLAM's fission reactor core into part of the fallout cloud, and so irradiate more territory downwind.

But this analogy requires care. For World War I, historians already knew who shot the Archduke, and why (desire for South Slavic independence from the Austro-Hungarian empire). But that knowledge proved irrelevant to understanding the war's actual causes. 15 years after WWI ended, educated opinion blamed the war on international arms merchants.^{43,44} By the 1960s, historians had reached rough consensus that the causes of the war were quite different and structural: alliance systems, imperial rivalries, mobilization plans, and railway timetables.⁴⁵ And during the 1960s that just-emerged structural consensus was challenged by further study, which emphasized the agency of German elites.⁴⁶

Understanding the cause(s) of COVID-19 presents a different challenge. Here, the precipitating event, the circumstances in which the SARS-CoV-2 pathogen entered and began circulating in the human population, is not understood. For WWI, the precipitating event was incidental to the principal causes. For COVID-19, entry into the human population and start of fast circulation constitute both etiological and sufficient cause. Moreover, the combination of entry and the circumstances that led up to entry together will define the principal causes.

Yet continuing uncertainty about the precipitating event need not prevent consideration of conditions that made entry into the human population possible.

If SARS-CoV-2 was a zoonosis, if it entered the human population from human contact with an animal host, deeper understanding will require attention to changes in urban diets, farming methods, and flows of animals and animal products. Prevention of the next pandemic might require tighter enforcement of game laws and crackdowns on live animal smuggling. If SARS-CoV-2 entered the population as a consequence of R&D activity, historians will examine how recombinant DNA technology enabled viral engineering work and the development of reverse-genetic systems, and placed directed viral evolution via generation of diversity and serial passage on firm molecular-biological ground. In the U.S. they may look to the great expansion in the number of high containment biological facilities after 9/11; in other countries, to the increase in the number of such facilities and their transformation into symbols of national power, akin to space programs, and the widespread disregard of or at least erosion of commitment to international conventions such as the Biological Weapons Convention. The prescription for preventing the next pandemic might then involve new treaties, a reduction in the global biocontainment escape surface, and strict supervision of high containment work.

Such systemic enablers, ecological or technological, and possible approaches to lowering the risk of entry into the human population, merit consideration now, even while uncertainty over the path the virus took persists. Kadlec's report describes waters that are still muddy. But I believe that future historians will look back on it, and on the

⁴³ Helmuth C. Engelbrecht and Frank C. Hanighen, *Merchants of Death: A Study of the International Armament Industry* (Dodd, Mead & Company, 1934).

⁴⁴ U.S. Senate, Special Committee Investigating the Munitions Industry, *Munitions Industry: Report on Government Manufacture of Munitions*, 74th Cong., 2nd sess., 1936, S. Rept. 944, pt. 7, <https://archive.org/details/munitionsindustr36unit/page/n5/mode/2up>.

⁴⁵ James Joll, *The Origins of the First World War*, 2nd ed. (London: Longman, 1992).

⁴⁶ Fritz Fischer, *Germany's Aims in the First World War* (New York: W. W. Norton and Company, 1967).

numerous particles of evidence that make it so turbid, and find that Kadlec's work moved human understanding a millimeter closer to that knowable truth.

About the Author

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